

FOCUSING ON VERBS EXPRESSING THE REALIZATION OF PURPOSE IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The given thesis focuses on determining a purpose and verbs expressing the steps of achieving the goal: the verbs are classified into several groups like intention, wish, plan, trying and so on. Theoretical views of linguists on the expression of realizing a goal are discussed. The thesis can be of benefit to those who are interested in syntactic semantics.

Keywords: meaning of purpose, action verbs, intention, attempt, infinitive, gerund.

Introduction

The category of finality is of great importance in the construction and formation of the content of a sentence. In linguistics, a number of studies have been conducted on the study of the expression of purpose, and this concept has been studied by linguists on the basis of different approaches. In this paper we study verbs expressing purpose, its origin and the stages of its implementation. To divide verbs into groups, quantitative and qualitative methods, methods of distributional analysis and classification are used.

Purpose is an important activity in a person's life, and the process of its implementation consists of several stages of activity. Since purpose is an activity, when expressing it, words from the verb group are mainly used. We study verbs denoting purpose and the stages of its implementation, dividing them into groups according to structure and meaning.

Literature review and discussion

Verbs expressing purpose have been the subject of a number of studies, and terms such as *finit verbs* and *intensional verbs* have also been applied to them. In particular, A.A.Shakhmatov, taking into account that verbs of purpose can be combined with nouns according to their substantial features, divides them into two classes: intensional verbs (Vint) and nointensional verbs (Vnoint). The first group can include verbs that denote properties which are different from the subject, substance or object, for example: *build, result, kill, collide (with), consist (of), cut, effect* [1, с. 17]. The second group includes verbs that are performed directly by the subject, for example, *sneeze, sleep, smile, laugh, snore, sniff*.

The peculiarity of verbs expressing purpose is that their content depends on the meaning of the lexical units surrounding it, that is, their distribution is important. Our main task is to analyze verbs of action or state aimed at achieving a certain goal. There is a group of verbs denoting desire, intention, processes of preparation and attempts to realize the goal.

The distribution of verbs of purpose consists of voluntary and obligatory units. The obligatory distribution has the following model: *N/Prn + Vint/ + to Infinitive/Gerund*, where the noun or pronoun is an animate person and is a potential performer of the action expressed by the infinitive or gerund.

The men contemplated finding the treasure awhile in blissful silence. (MTTS, 182)

I prayed the Lord to let me live to see it, son. (PAPT, 50)

Also, in a sentence, verbs can be combined with the conjunction *and*, and can be found as homogeneous members of a sentence. Here the infinitive model *N + Vint + and + Infinitive* is formed.

Oh, go long with you, Tom, before you aggravate me again. And you try and see if you can't be a good boy, for once, and you needn't take any more medicine. (MTTS, 95)

In addition, depending on the syntactic possibilities of the sentence, a prepositional phrase can be used instead of an infinitive or gerund, for example:

There was a tone of despotism in the urgency of the very reproaches by which, he aimed at goading the oppressed into rebellion against the oppressor. (Ch. Bronte, int. res.)

In the English language, when the verb *try* is combined with an infinitive, it means trying hard to perform an action, and that action is important to the subject, and the subject intends to perform that action.

As mentioned above, verbs are divided into groups depending on the stages to achieving the goal. Of these, we analyze verbs expressing the intention of the action. Here we rely on the opinions of Sh.Bally, Z.D.Popova and I.V.Khoroshunova [2, 3, pp. 34-35]. In her study, Yu.V.Zayukova schematically described verbs denoting the goal and the stages leading to it, and their subgroups [3, p. 47].

Conclusions

From the examples given, we can conclude that verbs expressing purpose cannot fully express the required content when used alone; they always include units that functionally complement the structure of the sentence, that is, the presence of lexical units denoting desire, intention, goal, action, etc. is required. If the requirements for

the scope of units are violated, the desired content of the goal is not achieved. However, verbs denoting the goal may be ellipsis, in this case the final syntaxeme is revealed by restoring it.

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